

Communication Packages

– Summary of Communication Activities

Smart Energy Services to Improve the Energy Efficiency of the European Building Stock

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This report contains a summary of communication activities in the first four (4) months of project SENSEI. It is the first of three reports during the lifetime of the project. Next reports will be in month 22 and 35 of the project.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
GA	Grant Agreement
KoM	Kick-off Meeting
P4P	Pay-for-Performance
DCP	Dissemination and Communication Plan
EC	European Commission
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Executive summary

SENSEI is a project based on thorough research in energy efficiency. SENSEI will put research into action and will in this process involve market players in this process. Communication activities towards market players in the energy and financial sector is crucial to achieve a go-to-market success. Therefore, it is highly important to engage in effective communication activities towards potential stakeholders to increase engagement in the co-creation process of P4P in the European energy market.

Up to month four in the project SENSEI much effort has been put into establishing the fundamentals in communication and dissemination such as project presentation, flyer, infographics. Still some fine-tuning needs to be done and further actions have to be taken to bring the essentials up front for communication purposes.

The project consortium has during the first months of the project lifetime identified a challenge in the flow of knowledge and content internally. This challenge is still discussed, and the solution is to establish an Editorial Board. The Editorial Board was proposed to bring the partner's expert closer to the communication table to mitigate misconceptions and unfortunate interpret of P4P in the external communication of P4P. Further steps will soon be taken in the consortium as soon as the purpose of the Editorial Board is clear.

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope of the Deliverable

The present deliverable, Summary of Communication Activities, is developed to sum up on ongoing activities regarding reaching out to potential collaborators. This includes other EU projects and companies that have important information and knowledge for project SENSEI to incorporate. Initially, the purpose of Summary of Communication Activities is to pave the road for further communication activities and point out essential communication needs to reach the project goal.

GECO Global is the leader of the production of D3.3 and will lead the ongoing communication activities during the project lifetime. During Kick-off Meeting (KoM), a cluster of partners in communication, dissemination and outreach was established (Cluster 3). The task “Communication and dissemination” is a dynamic process, and this document is for reporting on the progressions in this process.

Description of task 3.3 in the Grant Agreement:

The project will produce three communication packages, which aim at broad communication of the intentions and results of the project:

1. Presentation on the project, aims and objectives, methods, consortium, etc. at the beginning of the project. This will include the production of a flyer, poster, press release, a short presentation video (scribing technique), and communication design templates. The video will be published on the project’s website, on YouTube and other video sharing systems.
2. Communication of results halfway through the project. This will include a policy brief, press release on main results, and a presentation to be used by the partners for presenting the SENSEI results at meetings, conferences, etc.
3. Communication of results at the end of the project. This will include a policy brief, and a summary presentation to recap the key findings and results tailored for the project partners’ own use enabling them to exploit the project work post-SENSEI. The final communication package will also include a video (scribing techniques), which documents the results of the project. It will be published on the project’s website, on YouTube and other video sharing systems.

Led by GECO with the support of RAP and DBT, and FACTOR4 (to help craft the content from the ESCOs’ perspective), OMNIA ENERGIA (to help craft the content from the energy providers’ perspective) and GENCAT (to help craft the content from the building owners’ perspective).

1.2 Structure of the Document

The present document reports on communication activities in project SENSEI which is bullet 1:

Presentation on the project, aims and objectives, methods, consortium, etc. at the beginning of the project. This will include the production of a flyer, poster, press release, a short

presentation video (scribing technique), and communication design templates. The video will be published on the project's website, on YouTube and other video sharing systems.

In order to deliver a proper description of this document, it will include the following:

1. Initial preparation steps towards project KoM.
2. Initial establishment of communication channels.
3. Project profile, presentation and communication design templates.
4. Project website and online presence
5. Project flyer, infographics and poster
6. Identification of key messages and selling points
7. Press release and initial invitation to stakeholders
8. Partners online presentation of the project and e-news
9. Initial description and first version of the presentation video
10. Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP)
11. Collaboration with other EU projects
12. Scientific publications and dissemination of knowledge

The report contains a summary of communication activities in the first four (4) months of project SENSEI. It is the first of three reports during the lifetime of the project. Next reports will be in month 22 and 35 of the project.

2 Communication Activities

2.1 Preparations

2.1.1 Initial preparation steps towards project Kick-off meeting

In preparation for the KoM, a corporate communication profile was drafted. The WPL of Communication and Dissemination did some initial preparations to ensure that all partners got aligned in what was expected from them in project dissemination and communication activities. By providing a corporate project profile and presenting according to the guidelines, it was possible to stress the importance of the communication and branding of the project.

The WP leader prepared prior to the KoM:

1. Initial establishment of communication channels.
2. Project profile, presentation and communication design templates.

2.1.2 Initial establishment of communication channels

The social media channels like LinkedIn.com, Twitter.com and Youtube.com were established. SENSEI is present on selected social media networks. These are crucial for the overall communication and dissemination activities and will be visible on relevant pages of the website. Bridging the gap between the SENSEI website and social media profiles, will be

essential to spread messages through the right digital channels to the right target group at the right time.

Figure 1: Three (3) social media channels in project SENSEI

Initially, social media channels were used to communicate the settlement of the consortium and the initial organizing of WPs and tasks at the KoM. In addition, the consortium will use social media to ensure that information is shared with relevant audiences timely. Partners will extend the knowledge of SENSEI, distribute results on the go, and help create attention for the project’s events on social media. Regular tweets from the project twitter account (@sensei_h2020) will also work in collaboration with the project website, and stakeholders will be motivated to make use of Twitter.

2.1.3 Project profile, presentation and communication design templates

Prior to the KoM, the WPL started the production of a corporate project identity and introduced a draft logo and design templates that included presentation templates. Introducing a corporate identity is to ensure a common communication profile and from the beginning stress the importance of the communication from KoM to the end of the project.

The SENSEI logo is built up of a simple font set combined with a recognisable green clover. Each leaf carries a SENSEI message:

Stakeholder impact: Energy Efficiency: Investments: Market:

Figure 2: Initial SENSEI logo

During the KoM, the intention was to get feedback from partners on the communication profile. After the KoM adjustments were made, and the WPL made some alternative logos and send out a poll to the consortium for the partners to vote for their favourite logo.

Figure 3: Original logo and four (4) alternative logos for the poll.

After the logo poll, the final logo became the clover logo. The colours in the logo and a colour palette is a part of the communication profile.

	<p>GREEN #a3d888</p>	<p>Green, the color of life, is chosen as the main color, because it is associated with renewal, nature, and energy, as well as meanings of growth, harmony, freshness, and environment. Green is also traditionally associated with money, finances, banking, and ambition.</p>
	<p>PURPLE #727ca9</p>	<p>The light purple is the secondary color to the primary color green. Purple combines the calm stability of blue and the fierce energy of red. Purple is used in the font of the logo. Purple will also be used for icons and social media graphics.</p>
	<p>ANTHRACITE #4d4d4d</p>	<p>Anthracite is a chalky and earthy near-black or very dark grey. The color anthracite will be used mostly for content, outline and text.</p>
	<p>ORANGE #fff0ca RED-ORANGE #7e414e</p>	<p>Orange is an energizing, positive color. The light creamy orange will mostly be used as an alternative gradient color and light background for text or pictures. The red brown is chosen as a contrast color to go with the light orange and will be used for links and buttons e.g. on website.</p>

Figure 4: The colour palette of the communication profile

When the final logo was decided, the presentation and communication design templates were disseminated to the consortium. Six (6) templates make up the package of templates:

1. Powerpoint template 4:3

2. Powerpoint template 16:9
3. Table and Charts template
4. Deliverable template Confidential
5. Deliverable template Public
6. Meeting Minutes template

A picture was included for multiple purposes (templates, website, poster, etc.) and a simple design for presentation templates was produced.

Figure 5: The front of the presentation template.

2.2 Carried out

2.2.1 Project website and online presence

The SENSEI website www.senseih2020.eu will serve as main news and information hub for all dissemination and communication activities throughout the project period. The website is a key tool to increase project awareness and to target stakeholders effectively.

Visitors will find information about the project and partners, recent news, Newsletters, deliverables and upcoming events. Social media feeds are integrated on the website, thus being an effective way of keeping the website up to date.

WordPress was selected as Content Management System (CMS) for the website. This is an open source, license free CMS with flexible templates, various editorial functionalities and marginal maintenance costs. Additionally, Wordpress was selected because it is easy to integrate with the stakeholder support platform EngageSuite.

Figure 6: The structure of the website.

Initially, the structure of the website was decided. Secondly, all web technical features are incorporated such as Google Analytics for web analysis purposes, MailChimp to serve as Newsletter generator, SENSEI email verifications for contact forms, website validations for Google index, social media integrations and verifications at the website, multi-language plugin, GDPR compliance and Search Engine Optimizations. The SENSEI website is optimized for the Google Chrome browser.

Figure 7: The frontpage of the SENSEI website

The social media Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube are integrated into the website. Feeds from Twitter is present at the front page. All social media channels are initiated for dissemination of deliverables, press releases, partners attending events and stakeholder outreach.

Figure 8: SENSEI Posts on Twitter and LinkedIn

2.2.2 Project flyer, infographics and poster

The initial steps in developing the SENSEI flyers, infographics and poster are taken. SENSEI has a version one of a flyer, a version one of infographics and when the elements to go into a poster are ready, a version one of a poster can be made. SENSEI will throughout the project lifetime develop the communication packages and make adjustments in hand-outs and presentations according to preliminary results and final results in the project. SENSEI can present:

1. A version one of a flyer focusing on the importance of SENSEI towards the European market in Energy Efficiency.
2. A version one of amendments to the flyer, such as two examples of P4P and stakeholder benefits (second version will be like flyer's layout)

3. A version one of infographics “CASH-FLOW” presenting an example of a P4P business case and the interplay of parties.
4. A sketch of a poster that needs to be aligned according to the communication profile.

Figure 9: SENSEI flyer for printing hand-outs (A4 upright folded in the middle)

SENSEI HORIZON 2020

Developing smart energy services to improve energy efficiency of the European building stock.

The goal of SENSEI

The SENSEI project will design, test and disseminate an innovative transaction model to enable energy efficiency upgrades to be valorised through one or more of the following paths:

- Incentive schemes that aim at steering energy efficiency interventions towards measures that are beneficial for both the building owners and the power grid;
- Capacity mechanisms that compensate energy efficiency as a resource that achieves a permanent, continuous reduction on power consumption affecting the need for peak capacity or long-lasting ramping reserves;
- Programs that aim at financing energy efficiency without the risk of paying for unrealized changes in power consumption.

The SENSEI model will build on innovative pay-for-performance (P4P) schemes, according to which payments for energy efficiency are made only after the efficiency improvement and are based on proven and measured savings (using pre-agreed measurement and verification methods).

To achieve its goal, the SENSEI project will:

- Identify when and where energy efficiency can help defer investments in the distribution system or safely offset the need for ramping and/or peak generation capacity;
- Increase awareness on the P4P model;
- Propose and design new contractual arrangements to govern the transactions between the involved parties so that energy efficiency can become an exploitable resource for the power grid.

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STAKEHOLDER BENEFITS

Extended description of benefits

Benefits for building owners

Building owners will increase the benefits they get from an energy retrofit project, as well as turn them into an investable asset to attract private financing and minimize upfront capital costs.

Benefits for ESCOs

ESCOs will expand their market reach by collaborating with "energy efficiency aggregators" that create and broker portfolios of energy retrofit projects.

Benefits for power system operators

System operators will be supported in rolling out incentive schemes that aim at steering energy efficiency interventions towards measures that are beneficial for both the building owners and the grid, and will become part of the value chain of energy efficiency improvements.

Benefits for utilities

Utilities will diversify their revenue streams by providing new energy efficiency services (along with energy supply services) and benefiting from the value that energy efficiency brings to the power grid.

Benefits for investors

Investors will have new opportunities to invest in energy efficiency P4P-ready energy retrofit projects that will be particularly attractive for investors due to increased and stable returns on investment.

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P4P EXAMPLES FROM USA

PG&E Cool Savers program (California)

Purpose: Demand-side management for EE and EE as grid resource

Sector: Residential

Efficiency enabling methods used: CallTRACK system

Price: ~\$5 cents/kWh and \$1.5/kWh for up to 2 years

Performance period: 2 years

Description: The utility will pay a set \$/kWh payment for weather-normalized gross delivered savings at the meter to third-party aggregators for residential savings across their portfolio of projects through competitive tender, behavioral, and operational interventions.

The aggregator Build it Green (BIG) delivers the Cool Savers program on behalf of PG&E, by providing incentives to help customers upgrade to new, energy-efficient technology designed to increase comfort and lower monthly energy bills. Customers will save money in the way they:

- Up to \$2,000 in rebates for new AC units;
- Lower monthly energy bills and greater comfort;
- Up to \$5,000 bonuses for top energy saver after 12 months.

<http://www.cool savers.com>

NYSERDA Business Energy Pro (New York)

Purpose: EE as grid resource and development of EE services market

Sector: Commercial

Efficiency enabling methods used: CallTRACK system

Price: Call

Performance period: 3 years

Description: NYSERDA and a utility partner will select "Portfolio Managers", i.e. third-party service providers, who will engage with businesses to implement energy efficiency solutions. Portfolio Managers can achieve energy savings goals by offering a range of energy efficiency improvements over time and by establishing relationships to re-engage with their participating customers. The goal is to increase the likelihood of sustained savings, opening new options for testing different approaches and business models.

Energy savings from participating customers will be measured and aggregated on an ongoing basis to calculate the Portfolio Manager's performance to be compensated by the utility over time (e.g. three years).

After an initial intervention with the customer, Portfolio Managers will have access to individual customer and aggregated portfolio data, providing analytics and insights into realized savings and opportunities.

<http://www.nyserda.ny.gov/EE/Programs/Commercial-Business-Energy-Pro>

Figure 10: Amendments to flyer focusing on stakeholder benefits and two examples from USA.

Figure 11: Infographics to go into presentations and posters. Infographic is on website as well.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 847066

Figure 12: An initial version of a SENSEI poster.

2.2.3 Identification of key messages and selling points

The GA has preliminary outlined key messages (table 2.2) and stakeholders. Key messages that will be conveyed to stakeholders. The purpose of the key messages is to target the communication according to stakeholders and the purpose of selling points is to talk the “business language” targeted the different stakeholders. Identification of key messages and selling points will be a part of the DCP (D3.1) delivered M6. At this stage some preliminary key messages and selling points can be presented.

Stakeholders groups	Benefits	Key messages	Essence	Selling points
Building owners	Building owners will increase the benefits they get from an energy retrofit project, as well as turn them into an investable asset to attract private financing and minimize upfront capital costs.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Credible investment opportunities - Attracting capital in energy efficiency - Refurbishment of buildings - New revenue stream - Increased building value - Frees up capital - Installation of smart metering - M&V support in the different transactions between the parties 	A new revenue stream	Improvements of building, installations and maintenance. Building Owners can benefit by getting more private investors involved in retrofit of buildings with the aim of energy efficiency. Besides reducing CO2 (productive buildings), building owners can get happier tenants (comfortable buildings). Building owners get buildings of higher value.
EE Project developers, ESCOs, aggregators, EPC facilitators	ESCOs will expand their market reach by collaborating with “energy efficiency aggregators” that create and broker portfolios of energy retrofit projects.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - New business opportunities and business modelling. - Intermediaries will get more instruments for business. - Business models developed will benefit players and the value chain in the energy market. 	New business models	Cash-flow can be delivered through an Energy Performance Contracting (EPC) with the utility and does not rely on repayment by the building owner or the tenants. An agreement can be long-term and generate many more years of cash flow, and hence, can both finance and maintain much deeper efficiency installations.
Power system operators	System operators will be supported in rolling out incentive schemes that aim at steering energy efficiency interventions towards measures that are beneficial for both the building owners and the grid and will become part of the	Smart design of incentives for energy efficiency (permanently reducing energy consumption) can also lead to increase capacity for buildings to provide flexibility services to the grid.	Bringing the cost down	When end-users save energy during the grid’s critical times, energy efficiency can serve as a system capacity resource and/or defer distribution system infrastructure upgrades. Secondly, P4P can reduce costs in the energy system by providing flexibility and capacity reduction. Instead of investing in a new energy plant, P4P

	value chain of energy efficiency improvements.			programs can to a certain extent prolong investments in wires and cables.
Utilities, Energy providers	Utilities will diversify their revenue streams by providing new energy efficiency services (along with energy supply services) and benefiting from the value that energy efficiency brings to the power grid.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - New load management resource - Location-specific and reliable - Only pay for units received - Rate-based: Earnings opportunity - No gross revenue loss - No unit sale loss 	Avoid the death spiral	<p>The power system will benefit from an increased value of an energy efficiency intervention. Energy Providers will be able to provide building owners incentives for load reduction.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pays only for the actual metered energy savings. - P4P creates a standard – and powerful – encouragement to the developer and investor to make sure the efficiency is delivered and stays persistent. - Efficiency becomes locally provable and so locally targetable.
Investors	Investors will have new opportunities to invest in energy efficiency: P4P-ready energy retrofit projects will be particularly attractive for investors due to increased and stable returns on investment.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Long term reliable cash-flow from a stable, asset-based investment - Finance based on utility agreement - Stronger counterparties - Lower and rated payment risk - Well-understood instruments - Greater liquidity through utility-level portfolio aggregation. 	Long term contracting with utility	Better trade-off and return-of-investment. Besides green investment opportunities, Financial Institutions will benefit from more transparent Return of Investment (ROI) and profit from energy savings. Investors can get a fair deal of the revenues as a result of retrofit and energy efficiency.
Policy makers	P4P offers a solution to the logjam currently facing the market for energy efficiency. By metering energy savings over time, P4P rewards improvements that persist over decades, while also lowering the cost of evaluation, measurement and verification.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Domestic jobs - Environmental and climate benefit (CO2) - Instrument to balance the grid (flexibility in distributed energy) - Cost reduction (energy system) - Enhanced building stock - Price stability - No incentives required - Higher living standard and healthier buildings (population health) 	Scalable and flexible deep energy efficiency	Getting what you are paying for. In P4P programs, the players pay only for actual performance. Thus even if incentive Euro were added on top of a EE project, regulators could know that none of those Euros would be spent unless the contracted-for benefit actually showed up.

Table 1: Preliminary description of key messages and selling points.

2.2.4 Press release and initial invitation to stakeholders

After the KoM a press release was produced to present the project and overall scope of the project. A brief description of the project was released, and a targeted press release was prepared to be sent it out in due time as part of the engagement invitations to stakeholders.

Figure 13: Brief description of the project.

INVITATION to stakeholders to join

Take part in the development of a new innovative financing model to increase energy efficiency and maximize financial returns

15 November 2019

New financing models are needed to mobilize more private capital to increase the energy efficiency of the European building stock. The EC funded HORIZON 2020 project SENSEI is developing a smart energy service that can help accelerate the uptake of energy efficiency refurbishments in Europe, and provide value for the grid, and for investors. Making buildings more energy efficient is critical to meet climate goals, avoid the construction of new power plants, reduce grid infrastructure costs, and save customers money on energy bills.

Today most energy efficiency initiatives in the European building stock are funded by building owner collaborations and public subsidies. This is not enough to reach higher energy efficiency targets. New financing models can provide stronger incentives for investors to bring in more private capital into the market to increase the number of retrofit projects. SENSEI, inspired by USA-led experience in the field, will adapt the Pay-for-Performance (P4P) model (more on P4P in the box) for the European energy market.

Financing institutions and private investors face complexity and financial risk in the green transition in transition of buildings into greener buildings. P4P is a concept that can bring clarification of tradeoffs and more transparency in "What do you get for your investment?", both in terms of risk and benefit. Players with different interest in energy will get stronger incentives in energy transition, because they can share risks and benefits in financial investments. Energy efficiency will potentially give multiple benefits to players in the market, like higher property value to building owners, comfort to the end-user, new business opportunities to aggregators and more.

HORIZON 2020 project SENSEI funded by the European Commission started 1 September 2019 and had the first partner meeting in Brussels, 17-18 September 2019 (The project consists of 13 partners from 8 countries).

www.senseih2020.eu | @senseih2020 | #senseih2020 | [Twitter](#) | [LinkedIn](#)

For enrolment and more information:

Contact IECEP (Institute for European Energy and Climate Policy, The Netherlands) for more information on SENSEI project: Filippos Anagnostopoulos, filippos@ieecp.org

For more information:

Contact CIMNE (Centre Internacional de Metodes Numerics en Energinyaria, SPAIN) for more information in the technical/data field: Dr. Stoyan Danov, sdanov@cimne.upc.edu

Contact HERES (Heres Intelligence Single Member I.K.E., GREECE) for more information on the background: Dr. Sotiris Papadellis, spapadellis@heres.it

Pay-for-Performance: Rewarding savings instead of measures

Pay-for-Performance (P4P) links payments to proven savings. P4P schemes make use of an innovative concept to deliver energy savings through a flexible approach allowing innovation, reduction of costs and increasing customer value.

Most current energy efficiency programs work through rebates and incentives paid upfront for specific technical measures and estimated energy savings. In P4P schemes, those who deliver energy efficiency are only paid after the efficiency improvements have been implemented and on the basis of proven and measured savings.

P4Ps are emerging in the US as an innovative way to increase energy savings by engaging energy providers, attracting investors and motivating consumers to cut energy consumption. With increased confidence in its performance, energy efficiency can be rewarded as an energy system resource.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 847066.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 847066.

Figure 14: Press release will be sent bilaterally with invitations with a targeted approach to stakeholders.

2.2.5 Partners online presentation of the project and e-news

The project objectives and potential impacts were shortly after KoM uploaded as e-news on partners websites. The purpose was to communicate to business relations who regularly visit partner websites. Below is a list of partners who has uploaded e-news of SENSEI on their corporate website. More partners will be added as the DCP is published.

Partner	Link to e-news on company website	Link to Newsletter(s)/other online magazines
IEECP	http://www.ieecp.org/project/sensei/	http://www.ieecp.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/IEECP-newsletter-5.pdf
GECO	https://www.geco-global.com/sensei/	
UNICAL	https://www.unical.it/portale/portaltemplates/view/view.cfm?93199	https://www.approdonews.it/giornale/efficienza-energetica-unical-nel-progetto-europeo-sensei/ https://www.lameziainstrada.com/cultura-e-societa/efficienza-energetica-anche-lunical-nel-progettoeuropeo-sensei http://www.lametino.it/Ultimora/efficienza-energetica-anche-l-unical-nel-progetto-europeo.html https://www.noidicalabria.it/investimenti-in-efficienza-energetica-

		passano-dalluniversita-dellacalabria/ https://www.calabrianews24.com/rende-l-efficienza-energetica-passa-dall-unical-con-il-progettosensei/ http://www.meteoweb.eu/2019/09/efficienza-energetica-anche-l-unical-nel-progetto-europeosensei/1318234/ http://ildispaccio.it/cosenza/223876-efficienza-energetica-anche-l-unical-nel-progetto-europeo-sensei https://www.calabriadirettanews.com/2019/09/24/efficienza-energetica-anche-l-unical-nel-progettoeuropeo-sensei/
CIMNE	https://www.cimne.com/webcimne/sigpro/Ficha.aspx?id=838 https://www.beegroup-cimne.com/portfolio/sensei-smart-energy-services-integrating-the-multiple-benefits-from-improving-the-energy-efficiency-of-the-european-building-stock/	
OMNIA ENERGIA	https://www.omniaenergia.it/progetto-sensei-ai-nastri-di-partenza-con-omnia-energia-protagonista/	

Table 2: List of partners who has uploaded e-news on corporate website.

2.2.6 Presentation of the project at events

Project SENSEI was presented twice at two different events in Italy. The two events were:

1. S3 Forum – Ravenna, Emilia-Romagna, Italy, 17 October 2019
2. KEY ENERGY – The Renewable Energy Expo, Fiera di Rimini, Italy, 5-8 November 2019

Presentations were disseminated at social media and copies of the flyer were disseminated to participants during the events. All events and dissemination activities in the project are tracked and monitored.

FORUM S3

**I CLUST-ER E LO SVILUPPO SOSTENIBILE:
RICERCA E INNOVAZIONE PER LE SFIDE DI AGENDA 2030**

I Forum S3 sono momenti di confronto aperti a tutti i soggetti del sistema regionale di innovazione, nati con l'obiettivo di suggerire in maniera continuativa politiche e strumenti di intervento per una più efficace attuazione della Strategia di Specializzazione Intelligente (S3).

Nel 2019 si è deciso di orientare i Forum S3 verso indicazioni di policy per la ricerca e l'innovazione, focalizzate sul tema dell'Agenda 2030 per lo Sviluppo Sostenibile

3 ottobre 2019 | Modena
Residenza San Filippo Neri, Via Sant'Orsola 52

8 ottobre 2019 | Bologna
FICO Eataty World, Via Paolo Canali 8

17 ottobre 2019 | Ravenna
Palazzo Rasponi dalle Teste, Piazza John Fitzgerald Kennedy 12

Registrazione

Modena, 3 Ottobre 2019

- CITTÀ DEL FUTURO - Nuove prospettive per un ambiente urbano sostenibile | Sessione Plenaria 9.00 - 10.30
- Parallela - Ospedali 4.0 e sostenibile 10.30 - 13.00
- Parallela - Rigenerazione e riattivazione urbana 10.30 - 13.00
- Parallela - Mobilità e sistemi di popolazione sostenibili 10.30 - 13.00

Bologna, 8 Ottobre 2019

- CLUSO, LA TERZA, IL CLIMA - Sistemi agroalimentari sostenibili | Sessione Plenaria 9.00 - 10.30
- Parallela - Alimentazione e salute 10.30 - 13.00
- Parallela - Recupero di sottoprodotti 10.30 - 13.00
- Parallela - I dati al servizio della terra e del clima 10.30 - 13.00

Ravenna, 17 Ottobre 2019

- RISORSE DI OGNI VALORE PER IL DOMANI - Sistemi produttivi efficienti e innovativi | Sessione Plenaria 9.00 - 10.30
- Parallela - Nuove soluzioni per il packaging 10.30 - 13.00
- Parallela - Materiali innovativi ed ecosostenibili 10.30 - 13.00
- Parallela - Efficienza energetica ed energie rinnovabili 10.30 - 13.00

[Dettagli personali](#)

KEY ENERGY

THE RENEWABLE ENERGY EXPO

5 - 8 NOVEMBRE 2019 FIERA DI RIMINI - ITALIA

organizzato da **ITALIAN EXHIBITION GROUP** | in contemporanea con **ECOMONDO** | keyenergy.it

Figure 15: SENSEI was presented at two (2) events in Italy.

2.3 Scheduled

2.3.1 Initial description and first version of presentation video

Two (2) videos will be produced in the project lifetime. Video No. 1 is a presentation video that explains the essence of the project.

[>> Link to first version of a SENSEI presentation video](#)

Figure 16: First version of the SENSEI presentation video

The purpose is to deliver visuals that in approximately one minute can catch the eye and the interest to visit SENSEI website to read more. Below is the initial storyboard for video No. 1 that will be produced by M4.

Time	Theme	Script	Graphics
00.00	<i>What is the challenge</i>	<p>Buildings alone account for approximately 40% of energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions in the EU.</p> <p>So, improving their energy efficiency is essential in the fight against climate change. But financing these improvements is often difficult.</p> <p>If we make energy improvements for buildings something investable, their decarbonization become far more accessible. This is the idea behind the SENSEI project</p>	<p>Rapid succession of buildings' smoking chimneys, Single family houses, Multi family houses, Apartment blocks, Offices, Skyscrapers</p>
	<i>What is SENSEI's contribution?</i>	<p>SENSEI will provide mechanisms to steer energy efficiency interventions towards measures that are beneficial for both the building owners and the power system.</p> <p>By doing so, we can design energy efficiency projects that are especially attractive for investors. This will improve the buildings we live and work in, and significantly reduce our carbon footprint.</p>	<p>SENSEI Logo</p> <p>Oversimplified , icon-based image of the power system</p> <p>Or, simplified sensei model graphic.</p>
	<i>Who can benefit from SENSEI?</i>	<p>Building owners get better and more comfortable buildings, improved indoor climate, and a lower environmental footprint</p> <p>Investors get green investment opportunities, and returns that are based on verified savings</p> <p>Energy system operators get cost effective options to ensure the stability and adequacy of the energy system, while pursuing its decarbonization</p> <p>The environment also wins from decreases energy demand, and reduced emissions of greenhouse gases</p>	<p>An icon for each category</p>
	<i>Where can you learn more SENSEI?</i>	<p>Learn more about SENSEI on our website [1 second break] and on our social media.</p>	<p>www.senseih2020.eu</p> <p>Twitter, LinkedIn,</p>
	<i>Outro</i>		<p>SENSEI and EU-logo</p> <p>Text: This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020</p>

			Framework Programme for Research and Innovation under the Grant Agreement No. 847066
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Table 3: Initial storyboard for video No. 1 – a presentation video.

2.3.2 Dissemination and Communication Plan

According to the project timeline, a DCP is D3.1 and will be delivered in month six (6). The DCP will contain a communication strategy and an action plan for all further communication activities in project SENSEI including dissemination deeds. The DCP will bring a detailed action plan and be an overview of:

1. Key communication messages to stakeholders
2. Plan for website development and forward online activity
3. Production of use-cases
4. Production of info-graphics
5. Posters for presentation at conferences, events etc.
6. Four (4) articles on different related topics (translated)
7. Four (4) press releases on different related topics (translated)
8. Production of two (2) presentation videos
9. Production of two (2) policy briefs targeted stakeholders
10. Production of a presentation for partners to use at conferences, events, etc.
11. Plan for partners to participate in dissemination events
12. Production of six (6) articles for project Newsletter
13. Plan for identification and activate network of journalists in the areas like green energy, renewables, construction and building, consumers, green investments, green innovation (technology, energy efficiency, etc.)
14. Plan for contacting media and press contact in Netherlands, Italy, Greece, Spain, Belgium, Denmark and Germany.
15. Production of three (3) webinars on different relevant topics
16. Production of one (1) policy event
17. Production of two (2) stakeholder workshops
18. Production of two (2) capacity building events
19. Production of content for stakeholder engagement (EngageSuite)
20. Production of KPI's and tracking of activities
21. Plan for collaborative events for bringing knowledge between EU projects
22. Plan for production of scientific publications

2.3.3 Collaboration with other EU projects

The first steps have been taken to bridge knowledge between SENSEI and other relevant EU project. The purpose is to ensure a collaboration for synergy creation. For SENSEI it is important to benefit from other project's findings and to create collaboration in e.g. workshops or other events of matter over the whole duration of the project. In order to avoid duplication of work, build on already produced sound analysis and exploit synergies, SENSEI

has identified a list of projects also funded by the EC. Below is a list showing the progressions in bridging.

NOVICE – New Buildings Energy Renovation Business Models incorporating dual energy service	SENSEI has contacted NOVICE and established collaboration. NOVICE participated in the first SENSEI introductory webinar about “What is P4P?”
TripleA - Enhancing at an Early Stage the Investment Value Chain of Energy Efficiency Projects	SENSEI has reached out to TripleA in order to organize a first webinar and arrange a EUSEW event together
LAUNCH - Sustainable Energy Assets through standardised, investor grade Energy Performance Contracts, standardised risk assessment protocols for investors	SENSEI has reached out to LAUNCH in order to organize a first webinar and arrange a EUSEW event together
PROSPECT – Peer Powered Cities and Regions	SENSEI will contact soon
EDI-NET – The Energy Data Innovation Network; using smart meter data, campaigns and networking to increase the capacity of public authorities to implement sustainable energy policy	SENSEI will contact soon
SHERPA – Shared knowledge for Energy Renovation in buildings by Public Administrations	SENSEI will contact soon
CESBA MED – Sustainable MED Cities, INTERREG MED Programme	SENSEI will contact soon
Sim4Blocks – Simulation Supported Real Time Energy Management in Building Blocks	SENSEI will contact soon
GuarantEE – Energy Efficiency with Performance Guarantees in Private and Public Sector	SENSEI will contact soon
FALCO – Financing Ambitious Local Climate Objectives	SENSEI will contact soon
InterConnect - A step in effective energy management	SENSEI will contact soon
AMBIENCE - Actively Managed Buildings with Energy Performance Contracting	SENSEI will contact soon
ENTROPY - Design and deploy an innovative IT ecosystem targeting at improving energy efficiency through consumers understanding, engagement and behavioural changes	SENSEI will contact soon
Dr Bob - Demand Response energy management solution optimises the local energy production, consumption and storage in real time	SENSEI will contact soon
TABEDE - Towards Building ready for Demand response	SENSEI will contact soon
RESPOND - Integrated demand Response Solution towards energy Positive	SENSEI will contact soon

Table 4: List of other EC funded Horizon 2020 projects that SENSEI will reach out to.

2.3.4 Scientific publications and dissemination of knowledge

Scientific publications/papers made during the project will be disseminated according to the GA. No scientific publications have yet been produced in the project but the means for dissemination of knowledge have been done been established e.g. Open Access, stakeholder engagement platform EngageSuite and social media channels.

3 Lessons learned and adjustments

The WPL in communication and dissemination has decided to establish an Editorial Board. The Editorial Board will be organized as a horizontal function supporting Cluster 3 and consist of partner's experts in energy efficiency. The Editorial Board is not a duplication of the Cluster 3. This action has been taken acknowledging the fact that communication and dissemination activities in project SENSEI need be organized better. See appendix 1: Editorial Board Guidelines.

By organizing an Editorial Board as a supporting function, defining the task of the board and describing the procedures within the organization, the goal is to increase the content flow and communication efficiency. Suggesting the Editorial Board is trying to find a solution to solve a problem of a "bottleneck" in communication tasks and to raise quality in the material's content.

The purpose of an Editorial Board is to bring the partner's experts in energy efficiency closer to the table for communication reasons. During the first months of the project the WPL in communication and dissemination has realized a great diversity of opinions internally on what P4P is, mostly because P4P in reality comes in such a great diversity of variations.

The communication that has to convey the important messages to potential stakeholders must be clear and concise, and the Editorial Board will support to mitigate that diverse opinions overtake and influence the communication and in worst case impact the results of the project negatively. In addition, the WPL in communication and dissemination can foresee that an Editorial Board can be beneficial later in the project to establish small agile communication teams e.g. story boarding, video production and composition of supporting guidelines.

The Editorial Board is attributed to the fact that almost all partners have PMs in WP2 and 3 (10 out of 13 have PM). Establishing an editorial board in an EU project is new to the WPL, and it is a need the WPL did not see in forehand.

Instead of non-experts in energy efficiency like GECO trying to guess what is the right message, then turn it around by getting the content right from the beginning and then communicate it. Establishing the editorial board is an attempt to prevent the non-experts to reinvent the wheel every time, communication people have to communicate – trying to optimize the flow of content by broaden the group of experts.

4 Conclusion

Deliverable D3.3 has its first due date month four (4) and wraps up what has been achieved during that time. Communication and dissemination started on day one of the SENSEI project in order to make the required preparations prior to KoM. Expectations in the project communication and dissemination were aligned among all partners during the KoM e.g. by establishing a cluster of partners named Cluster 3 Dissemination, Communication and Outreach.

In addition, the WPL in communication and dissemination has taken the first steps to establish an Editorial Board as a supporting function to Cluster 3.

The next D3.3 milestone will be month 22. The SENSEI project is a very important project in designing and testing P4P business models in Europe and has taken actions towards of raising the communication bar.

5 Appendix

Editorial Board Guidelines

Establishing Editorial Board

Cluster 3 (Communication, dissemination and outreach) had a coordination telco Monday 4 November 2019 and decided to establish an editorial board involving all partners.

The purpose is to optimize the flow of content and messaging that needs to be communicated. The task of the Editorial Board is to support Cluster 3.

It is crucial for the project to get experts in the editorial board in order to frame the communication content and prioritize the wording to ensure engagement of important stakeholders. We have to ensure that we put as big an effort into Cluster 3 as much as possible.

To ensure flexibility Cluster 3 suggests a structure and procedure outlined like this:

Structure

- The editorial board will be organized as a horizontal function and refer to Cluster 3. The editorial board will be a supporting function to Cluster 3.
- Most of the communication will be by email. The editorial board will have ad-hoc online meetings.
- When the editorial board is established, the editorial board will be included in the communication and dissemination plan.
- The editorial board will have to support all communication and dissemination activities in the project lifetime on request from Cluster 3 leader or a Cluster 3 member.

Procedure

- Each partner points out an expert to be a part of the editorial board.
- To get a good mix of knowledge/expertise in the editorial board, each representative writes a few lines about themselves in the field of expertise (Fill in the table below).
- Having this list of experts, Cluster 3 leader can ask for assistance and ask an expert to give feedback.
- In respect to partners internal planning and work streams, Cluster 3 leader can give short deadlines to mitigate “bottle necks”.
- Experts in the editorial board can at an editorial telco suggest new activities and/or send an email to all in the board.
- Before uploaded to website or send out, Cluster 3 will have to approve the content.
- Cluster 3 leader will upload to website or ask members to send out e.g. if it is at national level.
- In cases of content targeted national bodies in own language it can be send out by partners.

Cluster 3 leader: Carsten Gydahl, GECO Global

Cluster 3 members: Carsten Gydahl GECO, Filippos Anagnostopoulos IECP, Alessandro Celestino RAP, Marta Calvo Cortina GENCAT, Sotiris Papadelis HEBES, Giovanni Pede SINERGIE, Geert Goorden FACTOR4, Nicklas Badum DBT.

Editorial board: TBD

Q&A's:

- What is the difference between introducing “Cluster 3” and an editorial board?
Answer: Not all partners are represented in Cluster 3 and some persons in Cluster 3 are communication experts and maybe not experts in areas like energy efficiency, P4P, etc.
- Why not have the communication persons (who are in the global contact list in Dropbox) in the editorial board? Answer: The editorial board will consist of experts. Cluster 3 will approve communication material before publication.
- Can a partner have the same person sitting in the editorial board and Cluster 3?
Answer: Yes